

Mature Students and Alumni - Focus Group Questions

To better understand the university journey of mature students enrolled in a full or part-time course at UCD, researchers from the School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science used the questions below as a guide to gather participants' views and experiences on peer mentoring, interaction and support services available to them on campus. Please note the questions listed below were implemented as a guide when conversing with mature students and alumni. Not all questions were used and were re-worded or subjected to change during the focus groups to align with the topics being discussed.

Q1. How well supported do you / did you feel as a full time mature or part-time student at UCD?

Probing Questions

1. Are you aware of the support services available to mature and part-time students?

2. Have you used any of the following support services for students on campus?

2(a) Counselling 2(b) IT Support 2(c) Writing skills centre 2(d) Career guidance centre 2(e) Library services. 2(f) Access & Lifelong Learning; Mature Student Advisers. 2(g) None of the above.

3. Was your UCD / course orientation adequate in your opinion?

4. Were you assigned a peer mentor in your first year at UCD, and if so did you maintain contact with them?

5. Have your fellow classmates shared information about support resources on campus?

6. Any fora where mature learners meet for peer support? Is it encouraged?

7. Were you assigned a peer mentor in your first year at UCD, and if so did you maintain contact with them as you progressed through your course?

Student Advisers - Focus Group Questions

Following focus group interviews with mature students and alumni, the researchers held two focus group interviews with student advisers at University College Dublin. The purpose of this was to validate and / or challenge their opinions and experiences. Please note the questions the researchers used below were implemented as a guide when conversing with the student advisers. Not all questions were used and were re-worded or subjected to change during the focus groups to align with the topics being discussed.

1. How would you describe your experience(s) working with mature students at UCD?
2. Are there any interactions with mature students that set them apart from younger university students?
3. What are the biggest concerns mature students have while attending university and meeting their course requirements?
4. Have mature students informed you of any challenges they face that their lecturers are unaware of?
5. Do you have anything to say regarding interaction opportunities / optimising interaction among fellow mature students?
6. What is your opinion of the peer mentoring programmes run by UCD?
7. What are the pros and cons when operating peer mentoring programmes at UCD?
8. Based on your experience(s) with mature students, if you had to offer feedback to academic teaching staff, what would you want them to know?
9. Do you have anything to say that has not been covered in this focus group interview?